

1 **The exhaustion program and senescence program are intrinsically linked.**

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6 Exhaustion was first described in 1998 and described in molecular detail in the subsequent decade as a
7 cellular state of the cytotoxic T-cell engaged in chronic viral infections characterized by activation of
8 exhaustion markers at the cell surface including PD-1 (CD274), loss of effector functions and metabolic
9 dysfunction. We present extensive evidence here demonstrating that the senescence program activated
10 by oncogenes like KRas (oncogene-induced senescence) as a cellular restriction against transformation
11 and bypassed by mutant variants of oncogenes like KRas G12V and G12D is intrinsically linked to the
12 exhaustion program. Senescence in non-hematopoietic derived human tissues was characterized by
13 expression of markers including TIGIT and PD-1, and likewise, the exhaustion program was defined by
14 expression and modulation of key features of the senescence program, including cyclin dependent kinase
15 inhibitor *CDKN* family gene expression and the epigenetic molecule that serves elusive functions in
16 proliferation, EZH2.
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Results

We measured total transcription in young and aged human fibroblasts.

Transcription factors central to activation of the exhaustion program, BATF2 and THEMIS2 were transcriptionally activated; TOX induction was also observed.

Figure 1: The exhaustion program is mobilized in naturally senescent (aged) human cells.

GSE262932

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
116071	1.62E-06	0.43	-4.7959174	-2.0623778	56.46	BATF2	2309/	
9473	5.81E-03	0.314	-2.7584936	-0.8667121	101.94	THEMIS2	5552/	
9760	7.73E-03	0.324	-2.6636044	-0.8642553	96.86	TOX	5812/	

Less significant but perceptible changes in other genes of the TOX family were measured.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
100505501	1.72E-01	0.692	-1.3660717	-0.9455536	22.88	TOX-DT	10208/	
84969	1.81E-01	0.283	-1.3386297	-0.3788976	260.02	TOX2	10331/	
9878	8.22E-01	0.175	0.2245825	0.0393384	1393.42	TOX4	15779/	

At the cell membrane, senescence in young and aged human fibroblasts was accompanied by activation of TIGIT and silencing of the ligand for inhibitory receptor PD1, PD-L1 (Pdc1lg2), as well as PD1 itself (CD274).

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
201633	1.64E-04	0.224	-3.7689949	-0.842941	793.89	TIGIT	3535/	
80380	1.06E-09	0.204	6.09945	1.247067	545.63	PDCD1LG2	1390/	
29126	2.02E-20	0.298	9.2612873	2.7563778	172.1	CD274	525/	

We detected important changes in expression of other genes from the Pcd family. Pcd gene expression changes associated with exhaustion appeared consistent in that Pcd family genes were nearly always activated and repressed but context-specific in that the specific Pcd genes whose repression and induction as observed was often different (here, and data not shown). Pcd4 was activated in this case.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
27250	2.83E-17	0.202	-8.4533951	-1.7037941	639.15	PDCD4	654/	
105377023	1.97E-09	0.276	6.0004741	1.6548987	161.21	PDCD6IP-DT	1436/	
22984	1.92E-08	0.167	5.6186408	0.9377891	1729.75	PDCD11	1656/	
7292	4.69E-12	0.273	6.9146152	1.8876271	152.39	TNFSF4	1032/	

This was accompanied by changes in expression of genes in the cell death program.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
90427	2.94E-15	0.443	-7.8935049	-3.4930141	78	BMF	766/	
598	2.24E-10	0.18	6.3436066	1.140967	2195.08	BCL2L1	1268/	
64919	1.82E-07	0.327	-5.2166146	-1.7073181	108.42	BCL11B	1923/	
255877	7.01E-06	1.588	-4.4934044	-7.1369419	14.72	BCL6B	2575/	
604	1.51E-05	0.183	4.3270377	0.7937108	723.58	BCL6	2746/17001	

Bcl6b expression was activated, concomitant with BCL11b induction. A bcl-modifying actor, BMF, was induced, with repression of BCL6.

Thus, together with changes in components of the exhaustion program, like activation of TIGIT and TOX, as among the most significant changes in gene expression when comparing total transcription in fibroblasts from young and aged humans (intrinsically young and senescent fibroblasts) emerged changes in the cell death gene expression program, like induction of Bcl6b, as well as both activation and repression of genes from the Pcd family, including Pcd4 induction. Importantly, we found that a gene of the TNF superfamily expressed at the plasma membrane, which possesses described functions in exhaustion, OX40 ligand (OX40l, encoded by TNFSF4) was repressed in aged, senescent fibroblasts.

We measured total transcription in a second model of cellular senescence, utilizing RNA-sequencing in young and senescent HUVEC.

Figure 2: The exhaustion program is mobilized in senescent human cells.

GSE155680

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
80380	2.01E-72	0.078	-17.998234	-1.403142	704.13	PDCD1LG2	471/	
29126	1.77E-31	0.0638	-11.672193	-0.745086	1266.13	CD274	1340/	
9760	1.31E-60	0.0973	16.422739	1.597481	459.22	TOX	603/	
84969	3.89E-01	0.1185	-0.862191	-0.102155	236.36	TOX2	12910/	
9878	4.61E-01	0.0567	-0.736981	-0.041782	1459.73	TOX4	13279/	
201633	5.22E-04	0.1627	-3.468979	-0.56428	122.88	TIGIT	6898/	
3902	5.43E-01	0.4852	0.607784	0.294896	11.9	LAG3	13675/	
27250	1.77E-51	0.0721	-15.094206	-1.089014	1049.53	PDCD4	739/	
22984	2.43E-21	0.0549	9.48471	0.520627	2374.92	PDCD11	1948/	
9141	5.16E-13	0.0624	7.2211	0.450506	1225.92	PDCD5	3000/	
5134	4.59E-11	0.0637	6.583752	0.419647	1214.83	PDCD2	3446/	
10015	3.77E-08	0.0456	-5.501354	-0.25076	4556.15	PDCD6IP	4381/	
84306	8.33E-08	0.1405	5.359777	0.753276	156.62	PDCD2L	4521/	
10016	1.27E-02	0.065	-2.492515	-0.161944	1095.05	PDCD6	8712/	
11235	6.18E-01	0.0857	-0.498198	-0.042705	650.01	PDCD10	14021/	
105377023	6.77E-01	0.1615	-0.417161	-0.067354	112.06	PDCD6IP-DT	14255/	
7292	2.69E-03	0.0504	-3.000992	-0.151191	2714.9	TNFSF4	7728/	

8995	3.09E-26	0.0856	-10.596467	-0.907243	579.93	TNFSF18	1622/
8744	6.99E-07	0.2834	-4.961571	-1.406158	40.48	TNFSF9	4926/15580
9473	1.40E-01	0.1727	-1.47558	-0.254842	110.43	THEMIS2	1186/
22807	5.73E-02	0.4112	-1.900842	-0.781713	16.97	IKZF2	10094/

In this second model of senescence (replicative senescence rather than senescence resulting from aging of human cells), the exhaustion cell surface receptor TIGIT was again activated. However, when considering senescence separate from aging (young vs senescent human endothelial cells as compared fibroblasts from young humans vs fibroblasts from aged humans), the PD1/PD-L1 system was activated: both PD1 (CD274) and PD-L1 (Pcdcl1g2) were transcriptionally induced. TOX was repressed here rather than induced, with very weak activation of TOX2 and TOX4. Again, PDCD4 was activated, and PDCD11 was silenced, indicating a potential critical role for PDCD family genes in senescence and exhaustion.

When comparing the transcriptomes of young and senescent HUVEC, here, OX40 ligand was again significantly differentially expressed, but activated rather than silenced. We found together with OX40 ligand activation, strong induction of the ligand for the GITR (TNFRSF18), GITL (TNFSF18), as well as more modest but still significant induction of the ligand for 4-1BB (CD137), 4-1BB ligand (TNFSF9). The data reaffirmed a relationship between cellular senescence, the exhaustion program, and genes of the TNF superfamily that function in exhaustion.

After establishing an intrinsic link between the exhaustion program and cellular senescence, including TIGIT, PD1/PD-L1, nuclear factors including BATF2 and TOX, and TNF superfamily genes that function in exhaustion like OX40 ligand the ligand for the GIT receptor, we studied induction of senescence by expression KRas in human cells in vitro (epithelial cells of the lung), comparing total transcription in cells expressing wild-type KRas to cells expressing the oncogenic KRas mutant G12V, where we recently observed, described and established homeobox induction by KRas G12V and concomitant bypass of senescence induced by wild-type KRas by KRas G12V (senescence bypass).

Figure 3: Components of the exhaustion program are mobilized during oncogene-induced senescence resulting from expression of wild-type KRas in human cells.

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Expression of wild-type KRas in AALE lung epithelial cells

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
8744	1.31E-14	0.1831	-7.7050961	-1.4105476	701.04	TNFSF9	364	
3604	9.97E-02	0.2459	1.6463817	0.4049005	271.46	TNFRSF9	9407/	
8995	2.29E-02	0.4424	2.2758383	1.0069322	28.26	TNFSF18	6771/	
8784	3.47E-10	0.2293	-6.2759706	-1.4390415	133.57	TNFRSF18	758/	
7292	2.22E-01	0.1965	1.2215697	0.2400411	173.92	TNFSF4	11568/	
201633	1.87E-01	0.4193	1.3195697	0.5533339	36.23	TIGIT	11027/	
3902	7.67E-02	0.598	-1.7703218	-1.0587231	15.02	LAG3	8831/	
100505501	6.02E-05	0.4221	-4.0121045	-1.6936324	27.83	TOX-DT	2573/	
9878	2.02E-02	0.1264	2.3221285	0.2935558	7848.4	TOX4	6625/	

29126	1.60E-02	0.1809	2.4086954	0.4358382	519.54	CD274	6298/
80380	9.41E-04	0.2701	3.3076856	0.8932977	80.05	PDCD1LG2	3845/
27250	1.33E-10	0.1011	6.4232034	0.649583	7556.42	PDCD4	701/
22984	6.30E-06	0.1281	4.5159612	0.5785815	12251.86	PDCD11	1937/
728613	8.92E-08	0.1528	5.3474487	0.8171308	380.22	PDCD6P1	1234/

Expression of wild-type KRas resulted in repression of both PDCD4 and PDCD11, unlike in the senescent state in aged fibroblasts and senescent HUVEC where PDCD4 was activated but PDCD11 was repressed. TOX family activation was not prominent in the case of wild-type KRas in the lung epithelial milieu but a divergent transcript encoded by the TOX family, TOX-DT, was induced. Weak induction of LAG3 was observed together with moderate repression of TIGIT. Importantly, the GIT receptor (TNFRSF18) was strongly activated, concomitant with repression of the ligand for the GIT receptor, GITL (TNFSF18). The ligand for 4-1bb, 4-1bb ligand (TNFSF9) was a second significant activated marker belonging to the exhaustion program found in senescence induced by expression of wild-type KRas in human cells.

Figure 4: Components of the exhaustion program mobilized during oncogene-induced senescence are reduced, enhanced or switched during senescence bypass that results in transformation of human cells.

ID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
29126	2.63E-05	0.174	-4.203744	-0.7322619	898.34	CD274	1033/	
80380	1.22E-13	0.217	-7.415044	-1.6121718	238.38	PDCD1LG2	247/	
201633	1.03E-01	0.362	-1.631491	-0.590464	61.29	TIGIT	5776/	
3902	5.50E-01	0.693	-0.597532	-0.4141603	12.86	LAG3	13480/	
84868	2.07E-01	0.582	-1.261275	-0.7335998	20.2	HAVCR2	7909/	
7292	6.83E-01	0.206	-0.408997	-0.0841377	220.31	TNFSF4	15470/	
8995	8.70E-01	0.387	0.163821	0.0634228	41.97	TNFSF18	18159/	
8784	6.71E-07	0.359	4.969604	1.7855472	52.67	TNFRSF18	715/	
8744	1.11E-01	0.217	1.591506	0.3449988	388.82	TNFSF9	5987/	
3604	1.24E-01	0.238	1.53661	0.3653644	311.42	TNFRSF9	6290/	
84969	5.59E-10	0.211	-6.201616	-1.3091902	920.25	TOX2	415/	
100505501	6.15E-03	0.497	-2.739608	-1.3622146	26.52	TOX-DT	2434/	
9760	5.43E-01	0.496	-0.608849	-0.3022457	22.47	TOX	13344/	
9878	6.43E-01	0.147	-0.463343	-0.0678896	10025.85	TOX4	14876/	
8320	5.18E-01	0.264	0.646002	0.1703059	126.68	EOMES	12986/	
9473	2.63E-04	0.174	-3.649417	-0.6364451	404.4	THEMIS2	1415/	
22807	1.21E-03	0.189	3.237275	0.6106428	434.82	IKZF2	1755/	
22806	2.22E-02	0.367	-2.287225	-0.8395136	70.86	IKZF3	3345/	
55509	1.23E-04	0.386	-3.840329	-1.4833787	47.12	BATF3	1259/	
116071	4.91E-02	0.275	-1.968058	-0.5416131	148.5	BATF2	4298/	
84306	3.45E-02	0.173	-2.113934	-0.3650412	2660.33	PDCD2L	3846/	
27250	1.26E-01	0.138	1.528052	0.2104544	9747.85	PDCD4	6340/	

10015	3.96E-01	0.129	-0.849342	-0.1097306	18165.5	PDCD6IP	11155/
22984	4.71E-01	0.148	-0.720512	-0.1067147	17255.24	PDCD11	12284/
10016	5.78E-01	0.165	0.556805	0.0916621	7554.57	PDCD6	13908/
11235	8.96E-01	0.192	-0.130527	-0.0250607	6966.74	PDCD10	18513/
105377023	3.73E-02	0.148	-2.082796	-0.3083067	942.52	PDCD6IP-DT	3927/

Finally, after establishing that the senescence program was characterized by transcriptional features that define the exhaustion program, we asked whether the exhaustion program was similarly characterized by transcriptional features that define the senescence program. In humans, solid tumors are frequently but most often (in those whose tumors are appreciated in the clinic) unsuccessfully populated with a population of cytotoxic CD8+ lymphocytes known as tumor infiltrating lymphocytes that for reasons that are not yet completely understood reach a dysfunctional state, immunologically impaired state-exhaustion. Thus, we measured total transcription in a cell type that is a natural (non-experimental), endogenous example of exhaustion in humans, the tumor infiltrating lymphocyte (TIL) from a cohort of humans with lung cancer; these cells were isolated and sorted from the whole blood based on expression of CD8, PD-1 and TIM-3 (HAVCR2): CD8+ PD-1+ TIM-3+ TIL. The cells were paradoxically characterized by activation of *EZH2* and expression of *MKI67*, a proliferative marker, but expression of cyclin dependent kinase inhibitor CDKN genes *CDKN1A* and *CDKN2B*, transcriptional hallmarks of senescence.

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Discussion

These data are consistent with findings from in vitro study of CD274 expression in breast cancer cells which demonstrate a cell-intrinsic cellular effect of PD-1 expression, wherein ectopic expression of CD274 resulted in key changes in telomere reverse transcriptase (hTERT) gene expression that we recently demonstrated were often associated with the senescent cellular state. Additionally, we found that a second immunologic process associated with enforcement of a tolerogenic (or reproachment of immunologic activation) state, expression of the aryl hydrocarbon receptor, was a central element of the senescence program. Together, we demonstrate here for the first time that the exhaustion and senescence program are intrinsically linked. The importance or essentiality of this relationship is evidenced by the function of TNF superfamily members that function as components of the exhaustion program in cellular senescence, including GITR, 4-1BB (CD137), and OX40.